

Tungro infection in IR varieties, IRRI farm, April 1981.

varieties and TN1 as the susceptible check were transplanted in 2.2- × 1.2-m field plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. A

row of tungro-infected TN1 seedlings planted around each plot served as a source of infection.

One week after transplanting, 100 *N. virescens* adults were caged on tungro-infected TN1 plants at the center of each plot. The insects were released 24 hours after caging. Treatments were replicated three times. Sixty days after release of the hoppers, tungro-infected hills were counted, and tungro infection was computed for each plot.

IR28, IR29, IR30, IR34, IR40, IR50, IR52, and IR54 had low levels of tungro infection (see figure). In general, varieties most resistant in the SBT also had the lowest tungro infection. In the IR varieties the degree of tungro infection in the field apparently is related to the degree of *N. virescens* resistance indicated by the SBT. ■

Response to insecticides of green leafhoppers from four sites in the Philippines

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To measure the development of insecticide resistance in green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens*, cultures collected from four sites in the Philippines were compared with a greenhouse culture. The insects originated from Pangasinan, Nueva Ecija, and Tarlac Provinces in Central Luzon.

Insecticide solutions of acephate, methyl parathion, MIPC, and monocrotophos were prepared. Three- to seven-day-old adult insects were anaesthetized and sprayed with 2 ml of the insecticide solution at rates of 0.125, 0.25, 0.4, 0.5, and 0.75 kg a.i./ha with a Potter's spray tower. Each treatment of 25 insects was replicated twice.

Treated insects were transferred to potted 2-week-old rice seedlings, covered with mylar cages (15.38 cm tall, 3.50 cm in diameter), and placed in 25° C to 27° C temperature, 60 to 80% relative humidity and 12 hours light. Mortality was recorded 48 hours after treatment and the computed lethal concentrations to kill 50% of the population (LC₅₀) were compared between colonies (see table).

Cultures from Palayan had 1.32-fold resistance to acephate and 2.02-fold re-

Resistance of field-collected green leafhoppers to insecticides (LC₅₀^a values). IRRI insectary, 1980.

Source of culture (Philippines)	Level of resistance ^b			
	Acephate	Methyl parathion ^c	MIPC	Monocrotophos
Palayan, Nueva Ecija	1.32 ^d	2.02 ^d	0.86	0.84
Santa Maria, Pangasinan	1.36 ^d	1.11	0.28	0.62
Rosales, Pangasinan	0.95	1.12	0.28	0.53
Pura, Tarlac	1.00	1.24	0.52	0.53

^aLC₅₀ = lethal concentration in kg a.i./ha applied in Potter's spray tower to kill 50% of the insect population. ^bLevel of resistance = $\frac{LC_{50} \text{ of field-collected culture}}{LC_{50} \text{ of greenhouse culture}}$. Resistance ratio of >1.0 indicates field culture resistance greater than greenhouse culture. ^cPENNCAP M formulation. ^dCultures with significantly higher (5% level) LC₅₀ values than the greenhouse culture.

sistance to methyl parathion. Cultures from Santa Maria had 1.36-fold resistance to acephate.

Methyl parathion and monocrotophos are probably the insecticides most

commonly used in the Philippines. The low level of resistance to the four insecticides indicates that resistance would not be a problem for farmers at the four sites. ■

Resistance of rice varieties to the green leafhopper in Southern India

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Resistance of rice varieties to the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) was studied in an international collaborative research project. Eleven varieties with known resistance genes, four varieties with unknown resistance genes, and resistant and susceptible checks were screened.

Test varieties were planted in seedboxes (60 × 40 × 10 cm) in 15 cm rows, replicated three times. Seedlings were

thinned to 30/ row 7 days after sowing. Seedboxes were infested with GLH adults (about 2/seedling), covered with nylon mesh cages, and maintained on galvanized on trays containing 6 cm water.

Damage rating began 6 days after infestation (DI) and continued to 11 DI. The 1-9 damage rating scale of the Standard Evaluation System for Rice was used. The rating at 9 DI, when 2 test varieties scored 8, was used to judge GLH resistance.

Moddai Karuppan with gene *Glh 7*, Ptb 8 with *glh 4*, and TAPL 796 with *Glh 6* had the highest levels of resistance (see table). ASD7 (*Glh 2*), IR8 (*Glh 3*), and ASD8 (*Glh 5*) were moderately resistant. Pankhari 203 (*Glh 1*) was